

Analysis of the Influence of Leadership, Work Environment, and Work Discipline as Intervening Variables on Employee Performance (Case Study at the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office)

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze further about the influence of management, work environment and work discipline on employee performance (case study: UPK Dinas Pengairan Dinas Lingkungan Hidup DKI Jakarta Province). The research method used today is quantitative research through questionnaires. The basic population of this study is UPK staff of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Irrigation Office with a sample of 50 (fifty) respondents. The test was carried out with validity and reliability tests, coefficient of determination (R^2) and hypothesis tests with the SmartPLS 3.29 program. The results of this study showed that: 1). Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; 2). The work environment does not affect employee performance; 3). Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; 4). Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work discipline; 5). The work environment does not affect work discipline; 6). Work discipline does not provide guidance in employee performance; 7). Work discipline does not attach importance to the work environment in relation to employee performance. This research meets several identified needs to examine how the influence of leadership, work environment, work discipline and employee performance is still needed in order to improve and develop human resource management.

Keywords:- Leadership, Work Environment, Work Discipline, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of a company in managing human resources is largely determined by the performance of its employees in fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. This aims to optimize the achievement of the success of an organization where in the process the organization must be able to face all challenges and be ready to face developing work situations.

The DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office is responsible for environmental protection and management as well as hygiene management in DKI Jakarta. The

performance of officers of the clean water treatment unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environment Agency decreased. This is based on three (three) aspects of performance appraisal, namely Attendance Discipline, Accountability for Completing Work, and Commitment Compliance, which is carried out once a year and used as a benchmark for employee performance. The table below shows the performance evaluation of personnel of the Hygiene Implementation Unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Water Administration Office.

Years	Target	Good	Moderate	Less	Total employees
2019	100%	80%	12 %	8 %	50
2020	100%	75%	15 %	10 %	50
2021	100%	70%	14 %	16 %	50

Table 1 : Performance Assessment of Employees of the Water Agency Hygiene Implementation Unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office

Based on the table above, employee performance appraisal data from 2019 to 2021 shows that employee performance is dominated by "good" values where in 2019 it was 80%, in 2020 it was 75%, and in 2021 it was 70%. Assessment of categories with a value of "medium" where in 2019 it was 12%, in 2020 it was 16% and in 2021 it was 14%. While the value category is "less" where in 2019 it was 8%, in 2020 it was 14% and in 2021 it was 16%.

Based on data sources collected with 50 employees, performance appraisals for "good" grades decreased from 2019 to 2021. This indicates that there is a decrease in performance as well as for the "moderate" value. Performance appraisal is a phenomenon that needs attention because employee performance affects the sustainability of the organization.

This phenomenon can occur because there are several factors that affect employee performance. These factors include first, the superior's bad feeling towards subordinates if they give a not high value which results in low assessment results which ultimately hinder the subordinate's career. Second, there is an inherent lack of supervision of the

employees concerned. Third is the superior's lack of concern for this assessment. The fourth is the lack of motivation of employees at the DKI Jakarta provincial environmental office, and the fifth is not in accordance with their competence with their work. In general, job performance appraisal systems are seen as the primary means of managing employee performance, sometimes considered an annual ritual of lack or even no action to be evaluated on an ongoing basis that is useful in shaping organizational culture and its benefits in career development are very useful in recognition of good performance.

Researchers have conducted a pre-survey of 20 clean water treatment implementation units of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Agency, from the results of the pre-survey that has been conducted, on the distribution of questionnaires, researchers asked respondents to choose three variables that dominate the most in influencing employee performance in the organization. Based on the pre-questionnaire results table, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents answered not the most in the group of questions leadership, work discipline and work environment. The other two groups of questions, namely compatibility and motivation, had no fewer answers, thus the two groups were eliminated as the chosen factors in influencing the decline in performance.

II. LITERATURE

A. Human Resourch Management

Human resource management is a series where in this process there are several stages, namely, recruiting, training, conducting evaluations, and giving rewards to employees. In addition, there is the management of relations with labor, health and safety, and legal issues [1]. Another opinion states that human resource management is a series of processes in which there is control over the acquisition, development, renewal, integration, preservation, and release of human resources that are planned, regulated, directed, and controlled to achieve various organizational and social goals [2].

B. Employee Performance

Employee performance is the output of work and work attitudes that can be done while completing tasks and responsibilities within a certain time. Increasing personal effectiveness increases organizational effectiveness because it is closely related [3]. Employee performance is also the result of records completed on work tasks or activities over a certain period of time, in this sense the notion of performance as a result of work and its contribution to the organization [4].

C. Leadership

Leadership is a field of study related to an individual can demonstrate, influence and control other individuals to perform duties and responsibilities in accordance with regulations or planned tasks [5]. Leadership can also be said to be the art and ability of individuals in a position to lead work to influence the behavior of other individuals, to believe that the individual is able to make a real contribution to achieving the vision of an organization [6]. Leadership can

also be said to be the science and art used to direct others and a community of individuals to work together, not belittle each other, to achieve organizational goals [7].

D. Work Discipline

Work discipline is the goatness and readiness, as well as the willingness of individuals to obey and follow the rules around them. Good employee discipline accelerates the achievement of organizational goals, while decreasing discipline creates obstacles and reduces the achievement of organizational goals. Work discipline can also be interpreted as a sense of obedience and obedience to responsible duties. This discipline is closely related to authority. When authority does not function properly, discipline is lost. Therefore, an authorized person must be able to convey self-discipline to take responsibility for his work in accordance with his authority.

E. Work Environment

The environment is an external institution or force that has an influence on the effectiveness of an organization. The environment has two parts, namely the general environment and the exclusive environment. The general environment is everything in the organization that is external and has an influence on the organization. The environment can be in the form of social conditions and other things of a technical nature. As for the exclusive environment, namely environmental conditions that are directly related to the achievement of organizational goals [11]. The work environment can also be said to be things that surround the individual who works that affect a process in carrying out the duties imposed on employees [12].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

From the results of the explanation above, there is a framework of thought used in this study briefly, namely:

Fig 1 : Conceptual Framework

Based on the framework above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

- H1: Leadership affects the performance of irrigation service officers in the processing unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Agency.
- H2: The work environment affects the performance of workers in the cleaning unit of the drinking water office of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Agency.

- H3: Work discipline affects the performance of employees in the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office.
- H4: Leadership affects work discipline in the water treatment unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Agency.
- H5 : The work environment affects work discipline in the Water Purification Implementation Unit, Water Purification Implementation Unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Service.
- H6: Leadership affects employee performance and work discipline is an intermediate variable in the hygiene application unit of the Environmental Office of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Water Administration Office.
- H7: The work environment affects employee performance and work discipline is an intermediate variable in the implementing unit of the drinking water treatment of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study, the authors used quantitative methods. The author sends an online questionnaire link via Whatsapp, Instagram, Facebook. The authors used 130 valid respondents for the analysis. In analyzing the data, the authors used the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with SmartPLS 3.0 to assess measurements and structural models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The findings of this study are based on gender, namely that the majority of female respondents filled out this questionnaire with a percentage of 52%. The most age is the age range of 24-33 years with a percentage of 78%, while the lowest respondents are aged 20-33 years with a percentage of 8%. The following are the results of data analysis that has been carried out.

Variable	Items	Outer Loadings	CR	CA	AVE
LEADERSHIP	KEP1	0.794	0.937	0.924	0.650
	KEP3	0.747			
	KEP4	0.765			
	KEP5	0.819			
	KEP6	0.813			
	KEP8	0.863			
	KEP9	0.821			
	KEP10	0.821			
WORK ENVIRONMENT	LK1	0.863	0.944	0.932	0.682
	LK3	0.911			
	LK6	0.734			
	LK7	0.822			
	LK8	0.906			
	LK9	0.844			
	LK10	0.781			
	LK11	0.723			
WORK DISCIPLINE	DK1	0.851	0.931	0.913	0.660
	DK2	0.776			
	DK3	0.742			
	DK4	0.833			
	DK5	0.817			
	DK6	0.727			
	DK7	0.923			
EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	KP1	0.782	0.922	0.902	0.630
	KP2	0.818			
	KP3	0.840			
	KP5	0.757			
	KP6	0.758			
	KP7	0.753			
	KP9	0.842			

Table 2: Construct Reliability and Validity Results

The threshold for outer loading, Compisite Reliability, Cronbach Alpha values is 0.7. As for the AVE value is 0.5. As shown in Table 1, all outer loading, Compisite Reliability,

Cronbach Alpha values exceed 0.7 and AVE values exceed 0.5 so it can be said that all variables are valid and reliable [13].

Variable	R-Square	Q-Square
DISIPLIN KERJA	0.432	0.269
KINERJA PEGAWAI	0.554	0.319

Table 3. Coefficient of determination (R2) & (Q2)

The R-square value for employee performance variables is 0.554 which means moderate. In addition to the Q-square value, testing shows employee performance purchase intent values greater than zero indicating that the model already meets the relevant predictive values.

Construct Relationships	Path Coefficient	Critical T ratios	P Values	Information
Leadership → Employee Engagement	0,546	2,835	0,005	Significant
Work Environment → Employee Engagement	0,537	3,406	0,001	Significant
Work Discipline → Employee Engagement	0,412	2,369	0,018	Significant
Leadership → Work Discipline	0,164	0,945	0,345	Not Significant
Work Environment → Work Discipline	0,218	1,301	0,194	Not Significant
Leadership → Work Discipline → Employee Engagement	0,221	1,620	0,106	Not Significant
Work Environment → Work Discipline → Employee Engagement	0,068	0,798	0,425	Not Significant

Table 4. Results of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing results that Leadership has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 2.835 where the value was greater than 1.679 so that this hypothesis was accepted. An indicator of leadership variables that has a major influence on employee performance variables is the KEP 10 indicator, which states that leaders in the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office are felt to always care about the problems faced by their employees by providing appropriate direction. The results of this test state that the leadership of the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office affects employee performance. This statement is supported by the results of a pre-survey that has been conducted that 80% where employees feel leaders are able to inspire and solve problems and leaders can provide clarity and understanding in completing work. This is also reinforced by the results of previous research which states that leadership has a role as a strong factor in human resource management, which can direct and also make other individuals complete the job immediately, have consistency in work, and can always provide encouragement and motivation to other individuals. Leadership also has an important role in influencing the achievement of the vision of an organization. This is because leadership is an important activity, where the realization of the goals of an organization.

Hypothesis testing results that the Work Environment has no influence on Employee Performance. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 1.301 where the value was smaller than 1.679 so that this hypothesis was rejected. An indicator of the Work Environment variable that has little effect on the Employee Performance variable is the LK 11 indicator which states that workplace security has been able to make employees work safely, the results of this study state that

employees do not feel safe so that the hypothesis has no effect. This is reinforced in previous research which said that the work environment has no effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis testing results that Work Discipline has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 2.369 where the value was greater than 1.679 so that this hypothesis was accepted. An indicator of the Work Discipline variable that has a major influence on the Employee Performance variable is the DK 6 indicator which states that UPK Water Agency employees are ready to carry out the work given by superiors. The results of this test state that Work Discipline in the Water Agency Hygiene Implementation Unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office affects the results of Employee Performance. This statement is supported by the results of a pre-survey that has been conducted that 75% where employees always try to carry out their duties properly as given by their superiors and are ready to accept sanctions if the work is not in accordance with what is given by their superiors. This is also reinforced by previous research which states that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis testing results that Leadership has a positive and significant influence on Work Discipline. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 3.406 where the value was greater than 1.679 so that this hypothesis was accepted. This can be interpreted that the better the leadership of individuals in an organization, the better the realization of work discipline by other individuals, while if a leader decreases or even tends to be bad, then the level of discipline of other individuals in an organization will also decrease. This is also reinforced by previous research on leadership affecting work discipline. The results of this test state that the leadership in the clean

water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office affects Work Discipline.

Hypothesis testing results that the Work Environment has no influence on Work Discipline. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 0.945 where the value was smaller than 1.679 so that this hypothesis was rejected. This can be interpreted that the work environment does not affect work discipline because employees are not comfortable with their work environment because the atmosphere of the work environment is less conducive as many people are not interested in entering the work environment. This is reinforced by previous research that states the work environment does not have a significant influence on work discipline.

Hypothesis testing found that Work Discipline cannot mediate the relationship between Leadership and Employee Performance. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 1.620 where the value was smaller than 1.645 so that this hypothesis was rejected. This means that the influence of work discipline cannot mediate the influence of leadership on employee performance. This means that leadership has not run well in work discipline so that it does not have a significant effect on employee performance because the leader where I work does not have the right and realistic strategy in every work agenda so that employees are still hesitant in carrying out work orders so that work is not completed on time. This is reinforced by previous research which states that work discipline does not mediate the influence of leadership style on employee performance.

Hypothesis testing found that Work Discipline cannot mediate the relationship between Work Environment and Employee Performance. The results of the inner model evaluation of this relationship resulted in a t-statistic value (t-value) of 0.798 where the value was smaller than 1.645 so that this hypothesis was rejected. This means that work discipline cannot mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance. This is because employees are less able to coordinate with colleagues on every job that has been given by superiors, resulting in late work in the process. This is reinforced by previous research which states that work discipline cannot mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results of research and discussion on the Influence of Leadership (X1), Work Environment (X2), and Work Discipline (Y1) as intervening or mediating variables on Employee Performance in the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office, it can be concluded as follows. Leadership (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2).

Work Environment (X2) does not affect Employee Performance (Y2) in the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Agency. The results of this study stated that employees did not feel safe so that the hypothesis had no effect. Work Discipline (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2). Leadership (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Work Discipline (Y1). Work Environment (X2) has no effect on Work Discipline (Y1). Work Discipline (Y1) does not mediate Leadership (X1) to Employee Performance (Y2). Work Discipline (Y1) does not mediate the Work Environment (X2) against Employee Performance (Y2).

Based on the results of the discussion analysis and some of the conclusions above, suggestions that can be given to complement the results of this study, namely making weekly review meetings to maintain and improve close relationships between leaders and employees, communicating service strategy targets clearly to employees at each weekly review meeting. In addition, in order to improve and maintain the atmosphere of an already comfortable workspace which especially in the selection of interior design, both in terms of color in the workspace, and others greatly support the state of mind of employees to work. This is because interior design, both in terms of color in the workspace, is an important aspect of work safety to increase the work efficiency of employees. Color affects the psyche of employees. Color can also stimulate emotions and the human brain. Limit activities in and out of people by making access cards in each room so that people who are not interested do not enter freely.

Provide regular training to employees on Emotional Spritual Quotient (ESQ) to maintain and improve employee norms. Leaders divide work according to employee competencies and abilities based on job appraisals. Update SOPs regularly in accordance with applicable regulations. Increase standards or quality by applying ISO standards in accordance with the needs of the clean water treatment implementation unit of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Environmental Office. Providing routine activities that improve communication between employees and leaders, one of which is sports activities. The next research can be suggested to examine variables that can affect employee performance with other variables because there are indications that other variables can affect employee performance.

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